

Monitoring Compliance with Senegal's Tobacco Products Packaging and Labeling Requirements six months after Implementation of the Law

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

As of December 2021, 22 countries and one jurisdiction in WHO African Region (AFRO) have adopted pictorial health warning labels on tobacco packaging, but only 13 have implemented them. In 2014, Senegal enacted a comprehensive tobacco control law, which requires strong provisions on tobacco packaging and labeling. The objective of this study was to assess the level of compliance with these provisions in Senegal six months after its implementation.

Methods

Data collection took place in Senegal's capital city of Dakar across 12 districts in February 2018, following the Tobacco Pack Surveillance System Field Protocol developed by the Institute for Global Tobacco Control at Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health. Unique tobacco packs were purchased from a total of 48 tobacco vendors, and compliance with new packaging and labeling provisions was assessed.

Results

In total, seven unique cigarette packs were confirmed to be legally available for sale in Dakar, Senegal. All packs complied with all health warning provisions (type, size, location, language, and quitline information) as well as bans on quantitative emissions yields. However, no pack complied with the descriptive constituents and emissions statement required on the lateral side, and four of the seven packs violated the ban on misleading brand descriptors.

Conclusions

AFRO countries have made substantial progress in adopting comprehensive tobacco control laws that bring them closer into alignment with the FCTC. This study found areas of effective implementation of FCTC recommended packaging and labelling requirements, as well as areas in need of stronger enforcement.

What this study adds:

- Only a handful of tobacco packaging and labeling compliance studies have been conducted in low- and middle-income countries, all of which have high rates of tobacco use. Research to date shows that countries are often not in complete compliance with all provisions.
- Gaps in knowledge include understanding the extent to which tobacco packaging and labeling provisions are enforced in low-resource settings.
- To the authors' best knowledge, this is the first study to monitor compliance with tobacco packaging and labeling in the WHO African Region and in an area of relatively low tobacco use prevalence.
- This study assessed compliance with Senegal's tobacco packaging and labeling requirements and identified areas of both effective and weak implementation.

INTRODUCTION

As smoking prevalence decreases across high-income countries, the tobacco industry is seeking growth in new and emerging markets, particularly throughout Africa. Consequently, smoking prevalence is increasing in areas of the world where it has historically been low. In accordance with the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) obligations, many WHO African Region (AFRO) countries have adopted tobacco control measures. These include tobacco packaging and labeling provisions proven to reduce consumer demand.¹ As of December, 2021, 22 countries and one jurisdiction in AFRO have adopted pictorial health warning labels (HWLs) on tobacco packaging. However, only Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Chad, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Madagascar, Mauritius, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, Seychelles, and Uganda have implemented them.

In March 2014, Senegal, a country with a low prevalence of tobacco use (6% in adults² and 9.2% in youth³), enacted a comprehensive tobacco control law, which among other measures includes strong provisions on packaging and labeling for all tobacco products,⁴ as recommended by FCTC's Article 11.⁵ In 2016, a Decree and Administrative Order issued specific tobacco packaging and labeling requirements, including rotating pictorial HWLs printed on 70% of both front and back of the packs, written in French, quitline information, descriptive constituents and emissions (C&E) information, and a ban on misleading brand descriptors (such as "light") and emission yields (such as nicotine).² These measures are proven to be the most cost-effective to inform consumers about the harms of tobacco use, to encourage smokers to quit, to prevent non-smokers from initiating smoking, to avoid public misperception about "less harmful" products, to increase consumer awareness of the chemicals in tobacco products and harms of smoking,^{6, 7, 8} and to strengthen communication with consumers about the harms of smoking. The new regulations were required to be implemented on all tobacco products sold in stores as of August 26, 2017.²

As a Party to the FCTC, Senegal is obligated to "develop, implement, periodically update and review comprehensive multi-sectoral national tobacco control strategies, plans and programmes;"⁹ and encouraged "to utilize their existing civil and criminal law to address issues of compliance and enforcement."¹⁰ Nearly 80% of the world's tobacco users live in low- and middle- income countries (LMICs), making the adoption and implementation of stronger tobacco control laws in such countries essential to curbing the global tobacco epidemic. Monitoring the

full enforcement of tobacco control measures is needed to uphold the laws' integrity, as well as the integrity of the government agencies tasked with their enforcement. Regular compliance monitoring also ensures that those who violate tobacco control laws do not enjoy an unfair advantage over those who comply. Only when fully implemented and enforced can tobacco control measures fulfill their ultimate purpose of improving public health. Given that only 13 out of 22 AFRO countries with pictorial HWL regulations have implemented them, compliance assessments are paramount to providing regional guidance for the advancement of packaging and labeling policies.

The objective of this study was to assess compliance with the key aforementioned tobacco packaging and labeling requirements in Senegal, 6 months after its implementation

METHODS

The Tobacco Pack Surveillance System Field Protocol developed by The Institute for Global Tobacco Control at Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health was used to systematically collect tobacco products packs and assess compliance with packaging and labeling.¹¹ The protocol, designed for LMICs, made it an appropriate choice for monitoring compliance in Senegal.

Data collection took place in Senegal's capital city of Dakar in February 2018, 6 months after the new packaging and labeling provisions were required to appear on all tobacco products sold in stores. Among Dakar's 19 districts, two were purposefully excluded: one due to a prohibition of the sale of tobacco products (religious reasons) and the other because the population and retail density were exceptionally low (tourist island). With guidance from a local partner, researchers chose 12 out of 17 eligible districts for data collection based on feasibility, geographic variation, representativeness of professional sectors (e.g., government headquarters, university campus), and socioeconomic status (4 high-income, 2 middle-income, 3 low-middle income, and 3 low-income).

Tobacco vendors selection

To select tobacco product vendors within each district, researchers followed a Vendor Selection Walking Protocol.¹² Local partners helped identified the four most common types of tobacco product vendors in Dakar: street vendors, kiosks, grocery stores, and gas stations. Data

collection in each of the 12 selected districts began at a centrally-located landmark or “hub” in a commercial center. Data collectors then systematically walked the surrounding area in search of the nearest tobacco vendor, from which they purchased all available unique packs. Then they moved to a second available vendor. If that vendor did not have any unique packs that had not already been collected, the team moved to the next nearest vendor to check for unique packs, visiting up to four vendors in each district (for a total of 48 vendors).

Pack collection

“Unique packs” were defined as tobacco packs that had at least one difference in an exterior feature or design of the pack, including stick count, size, brand name presentation, colors, cellophane, and inclusion of a promotional item.⁹ Only legal cigarette packs were considered for inclusion. Packs were determined to be legal if they displayed the required statement “Vente au Sénégal” [For sale in Senegal] on the lateral side and the authorization “FRA” code on the bottom of the pack. A manufacturing and sale authorization code (FRA code) is assigned to all products intended for human or animal consumption for legal sale in Senegal. This authorization is overseen by the Directorate of Internal Trade through the Division of Consumption and Consumer Safety within the Ministry of Commerce.

Pack coding

Once a cigarette pack’s legality was established, two independent researchers assessed its compliance with Senegal’s tobacco packaging and labeling provisions based on 3 sub-policy areas according to Article 11: 1) Health warning labels: type (pictorial and text); size (70% of the PDAs); location (front and back); text written in the principal language (French); additional text-only warning on lateral side; quitline information on lateral side; 2) Misleading information: ban on quantitative emissions yields (i.e., nicotine, carbon monoxide, tar); ban on misleading brand descriptors (i.e., “light,” “low-tar,” “slims,” etc.); and 3) Descriptive constituents and emissions information.

To calculate the size, the two researchers measured the HWLs with a ruler in the front and back of each pack. Packs were then coded, and data entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet for data cleaning and analysis.

RESULTS

In total, we collected 48 unique tobacco packs in Dakar. Forty-one were illicit tobacco product packs that included cigarettes (6), cigarillos (10), cigars (2), loose tobacco (2), and shisha (21). The remaining 7 were unique cigarette packs and were confirmed to be legally available for sale. All legal packs complied with all health warning provisions: pictorial HWL printed on 70% of PDAs, warning texts in French, an additional text-only on one lateral side, and quitline information on the other. Rotation of the warnings was not assessed, as this was the first round with a single warning.

All packs complied with bans on quantitative emissions yields and characterizing flavors. However, no pack complied with the qualitative C&E statement required on the lateral side, and four of the seven packs violated the ban on misleading descriptors, as they contained terms such as “Gold,” “Blue,” or “Slims.”

No legally available cigarette pack in Dakar was found to be fully compliant with Senegal’s packaging and labelling requirements (Table 1).

Tobacco packaging and labeling measures		Family brand and variant (tobacco company)						
		Davidoff Gold (IT)	Davidoff Gold Slims (IT)	Excellence (IT)	Houston (IT)	Marlboro Blue (PMI)	Marlboro Gold (PMI)	Marlboro Red (PMI)
Health Warning Labels	Type (Pictorial)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Size (70% PDAs)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Location (front & back)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Text-only on lateral side	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Texts in French	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Quitline	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Misleading information	No emissions yields	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	No misleading brand descriptors	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
Descriptive C&E information		No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Compliance with all provisions?		No	No	No	No	No	No	No
IT: Imperial Tobacco PMI: Phillip Morris International								

DISCUSSION

Globally, only few studies have assessed compliance with tobacco product packaging and labelling requirements. Studies conducted in eight former Soviet Union countries,¹³

Bangladesh,¹⁴ and India,¹⁵ documented non-compliance with some measures. Notably a 2016 study conducted in 14 LMICs with the highest smoking prevalence found that 72% of cigarette packs complied with all indicators.¹⁶

To our knowledge, this compliance assessment is the first conducted in the AFRO region, and it is significant because it identified only seven legal unique packs for sale in Dakar, all of which were cigarettes. Given the very low cigarette smoking prevalence in Senegal (4.9% in adults: 9.7% of men and 0.3% of women,² and 3.4% in youth: 5.6% of boys and 1.4% of girls³), this small number was not surprising. Two areas of low or non-compliance with packaging and labelling requirements in Senegal's national tobacco control law were identified: the presence of misleading descriptors (4/7 packs were non-compliant) and the lack of descriptive C&E information (0/7 packs were compliant). Packaging and labelling policies hold the promise of preventing uptake of tobacco use, and this is particularly important in a region targeting by the tobacco industry for growth.

AFRO has made substantial progress in tobacco control over the last decade with several countries passing comprehensive laws that bring them closer into alignment with the FCTC. It is thus puzzling to find packaging and labeling laws not well implemented, as the onus for compliance is squarely placed on product manufacturers who demonstrate little difficulty complying with such laws in high-income countries once government regulations are published. As in high-income countries, it is critically important that these policies be swiftly implemented. Additionally, they must be continuously enforced by government authorities. As the HWLs must rotate each year in Senegal, further research is needed to continue monitoring compliance with the implementation of subsequent rounds. Such monitoring can be used to drive enforcement.

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